

SOM 5 – Supplementary material on polish analyses (Micro imaging and qualitative classification)

Percussive experiment

Figure 1: Samples used for percussive experiments after cleaning

Bone Breaking (micro)

Figure 2: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with bone: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 3-1)

Figure 3: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with bone: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 3-8)

Figure 4: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with bone: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 3-9)

Figure 5: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with bone: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 3-11)

Figure 6: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with bone: a) 10x image of polish area and b) 20x image of a polish area.

Flint Knapping (micro)

Figure 7: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with flint: a) 10x image of a polish area b) 20x image of a polish area.

Figure 8: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with flint: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area.

Figure 9: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with flint: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 2-9)

Figure 10: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with flint: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 2-2)

Figure 11: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with flint: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 2-1)

Grinding experiment

Figure 12: Samples for grinding experiments. Photo: Eduardo Paixão

Dry acorn (micro)

Figure 13: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with dry acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-1)

Figure 14: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with dry acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-2)

Figure 15: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with dry acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-6)

Figure 16: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with dry acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-12)

Moist acorn (micro)

Figure 17: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with moist acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-3)

Figure 18: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with moist acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-5)

Figure 19: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with moist acorn: a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-7)

*Figure 20: Metallographic microscope image of a polish formed by experiment with moist acorn:
a) 10x image of a polish, b) 20x image of a polish area (Sample: 6-10)*